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there's
something
science
can do.

Policy Brief 2025/011
November 24th, 2025
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Issue/problem

The FDA [announced its plan](#) to alter the regulatory regime for bespoke gene-editing therapies for rare and “n-of-1” diseases. This “plausible mechanism pathway” (PMP) aims to approve individualized treatments for diseases that have an established a plausible biological mechanism.

Description of the problem

The FDA’s new pathway is designed to take advantage of the possibility that drug treatments could be specifically tailored to individuals through gene editing and RNA-based manufacturing. To [qualify for the PMP](#), treatments must be directed at the known biological cause, developers must have well-characterized historical data showing how the disease might impact patients if left unchecked, and they must confirm via a biopsy or preclinical tests that a treatment successfully edits its target and improves outcomes.

While initially focusing on rare diseases, the FDA has made clear that the new framework could also apply to [common conditions](#) that have no proven alternative treatments. The FDA’s approach to gene-editing and personalized therapies dovetails with the one to two-month [priority review process announced in October](#) for treatments designated as “national priorities.”

Results

The FDA’s approach follows the success of an in-vivo CRISPR gene editing therapy for [KJ Muldoon](#), who suffered from CPS1, a potentially fatal urea cycle genetic disorder that can only be treated long-term with a liver transplant. The FDA approved the experimental treatment plan after a one week review. The therapy [permanently altered the mutation](#) in KJ’s genome.

Lessons learned

The physicians who treated KJ [provided their feedback](#) to the FDA, with the intention of starting Phase I/II trials in 2026. While the PMP approach represents an expedited regulatory pipeline for innovative treatments, it also represents a marked departure from traditional regulatory practice by focusing on plausibility instead of robust safety and efficacy data.